

MAGNETIC STUDIES OF COLOUR CHANGES IN CUPRIC CHLORIDE

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Measurements of magnetic susceptibilities of cupric chloride, dissolved in various solvents, have been made under different conditions and the changes in magnetic susceptibility correlated with changes in colour of cupric chloride.

It is well known that cupric chloride shows green colour in concentrated solutions, while it gives blue colour in dilute solutions. These changes of colour in cupric chloride solutions were first studied by Solly (*Phil. Mag.*, 1843, *iii*, 22, 367) and Gladstone (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1856, 8, 212) who showed that a solution of cupric chloride in a small proportion of water is dark brown and the colour gradually passes through various shades of green, light green, bluish green, greenish blue and blue as the proportion of water is increased.

There are conflicting views regarding the mechanism of these colour changes. Ostwald ("Grundlinien der anorganischen Chemie", Leipzig, 1900) explained these colour changes by assuming that the undissociated molecules of cupric chloride are brown in colour and cupric ions (Cu^{++}) are blue in colour.

Thus there will be an equilibrium between undissociated molecules and ions depending upon the concentrations of the solution. Various shades of colour are produced as the degree of dissociation of cupric chloride goes on increasing with dilution. This assumption, however, could not be supported by the evidence obtained from spectroscopic investigation by Muller (*Ann. Physik*, 1903, *iv*, 12, 767) and Houston (*Proc. Roy. Soc. Edin.*, 1912, 32, 40). Wiederman (*British Assoc. Rep.*, 1887, 364) attributed the colour changes to the progressive solvation of the solute. It was favoured by Chuard (*Archiv Sciences Geneve*, 1888, *iii*, 19, 477) and Rudorff (*Pogg. Ann.*, 1862, 116, 64).

Donnan and Basset (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 81, 939), however, attributed the colour changes on dilution to the formation and dissociation of complex ions.

The above hypothesis is supported by Watkins and Denham (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1269) and Bhagwat (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 52).

Getman (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1922, 26, 217) is in favour of a compromise between the hydration and complex-ion formation theories. He infers from the study of absorption spectrum of copper chloride that in dilute solutions halides form complexes with molecules of the solvent and in concentrated solutions complex ions are formed.

From the brief survey given above it will be evident that some work is required to decide between the conflicting views regarding the mechanism of colour changes. The magnetic susceptibility determinations have proved like the study of other physical properties useful in giving valuable information regarding the nature of salts in dissolved state. Thus it was felt that the study of magnetic susceptibilities of cupric chloride solutions under different conditions may throw some light on the subject.

Work has been done by Bhatnagar and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 341; 1936, 13, 489) on colour changes of cobalt chloride in this laboratory and they have studied this problem by studying changes in the magnetic rotation and other susceptibility measurements.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The susceptibility measurements were made on a modified form of Guoys' balance. To maintain various temperatures, a silica tube wound round with a heating coil was used. In case of solute, susceptibilities have been calculated on the assumption that the magnetic susceptibility of the solution is equal to the sum of component susceptibilities.

$$\chi_s = \frac{\chi_{sol} - \chi_w(1 - C_s)}{C_s}$$

where χ_s , χ_w and χ_{sol} are magnetic susceptibilities of the solute, solvent and solution, and C_s is the amount of solute in one gram of the solution.

Magnetic susceptibility of conductivity water used in the present work was -0.720×10^{-6} . Cupric chloride (Merck's guaranteed reagent) was dehydrated according to the method of Sabatier (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1889, iii, 1, 88).

Water, *n*-butyl, *n*-propyl, ethyl and methyl alcohols were the solvents used in the present investigation. These solvents were purified according to the methods given in the literature and their various constants are as shown in Table I.

TABLE I.

Solvent.	Magnetic susceptibility.	Density.	Refractive index.	Boiling point.
Methyl alcohol	-0.665×10^{-6}	0.7908	1.3275	64.5°
Ethyl alcohol	-0.744	0.7898	1.3610	78.0
n-Propyl alcohol	-0.766	0.8035	1.3788	97.0
n-Butyl alcohol	-0.7587	0.8140	1.3952	118.0

These constants are quite in agreement with constants given in the literature. $\chi(\text{CuCl}_2, \text{anhydrous})$ at 35° was found to be 8.718×10^{-6} , and this $\text{CuCl}_2, \text{anhydrous}$ was used in this work.

The amount of CuCl_2 present in different solutions was estimated iodometrically. The magnetic susceptibilities of CuCl_2 solutions of different concentrations in various solvents were studied in a Gouy type balance and the results are given in the following tables. All measurements were carried out at 35°.

TABLE II.

Variation in magnetic susceptibility of CuCl_2 dissolved in water.

Comp. of CuCl_2 solution.	Magnetic susceptibility.		χ (CuCl_2 solid). Calc.	Colour.
	Calc.	Obs.		
34.13%	2.501×10^{-6}	3.343×10^{-6}	11.20×10^{-6}	Green
30.50	2.151	2.896	11.15	"
24.97	1.636	2.235	11.12	"
20.00	1.166	1.642	11.09	"
13.82	0.585	0.883	10.89	Blue
7.35	-0.026	0.105	10.50	"
3.82	-0.359	-0.299	10.28	"

TABLE III.

Variation in magnetic susceptibility of CuCl_2 dissolved in n-butyl alcohol.

Comp. of the soln.	Magnetic susceptibility.		χ (CuCl_2 solid). Calc.	Colour.
	Calc.	Obs.		
11.11%	0.294×10^{-6}	0.484×10^{-6}	10.43×10^{-6}	Green
9.04	0.098	0.248	10.38	"
6.90	-0.104	0.005	10.30	"
4.68	-0.316	-0.239	10.35	"
2.39	-0.533	-0.405	10.30	"
1.20	-0.645	-0.625	10.29	Greenish blue
0.405	-0.720	-0.725	7.584	Blue
0.122	-0.747	-0.750	6.716	"

TABLE IV.

Variation in magnetic susceptibility of CuCl₂ dissolved in n-propyl alcohol.

Comp. of the soln.	Magnetic susceptibility.		χ (CuCl ₂ solid). Calc.	Colour.
	Calc.	Obs.		
15.11%	0.666 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.993 × 10 ⁻⁶	10.87 × 10 ⁻⁶	Green
12.43	0.412	0.666	10.68	"
10.51	0.231	0.428	10.60	"
7.60	-0.046	0.006	10.40	"
4.45	-0.344	-0.279	10.18	"
2.00	-0.576	-0.577	8.70	Blue
1.13	-0.658	-0.668	7.87	"
0.58	-0.711	-0.719	7.39	"

TABLE V.

Variation in magnetic susceptibility of CuCl₂ dissolved in ethyl alcohol.

Comp. of the soln.	Magnetic susceptibility.		χ (CuCl ₂ solid). Calc.	Colour
	Calc.	Obs.		
12.94%	0.480 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.756 × 10 ⁻⁶	10.840 × 10 ⁻⁶	Green
10.40	0.239	0.447	10.670	"
8.16	0.030	0.185	10.620	"
4.79	-0.291	-0.135	10.315	"
2.40	-0.517	-0.482	10.180	"

TABLE VI.

Variation in magnetic susceptibility of CuCl₂ dissolved in methyl alcohol.

Comp. of the soln.	Magnetic susceptibility.		χ (CuCl ₂ solid). Calc.	Colour.
	Calc.	Obs.		
32.10%	2.348 × 10 ⁻⁶	2.675 × 10 ⁻⁶	9.738 × 10 ⁻⁶	Green
25.05	1.686	1.921	9.660	"
20.85	1.293	1.518	9.795	"
16.72	0.903	1.049	9.585	"
9.65	0.240	0.316	9.500	"
4.84	-0.211	-0.175	9.450	"
1.26	-0.547	-0.538	9.350	"

DISCUSSION.

In Tables II to IV are shown the results obtained by studying magnetic susceptibility of CuCl₂ in various solvents at different dilutions. Column 3 shows experimental values of magnetic susceptibility of the solutions. Column 4 gives the results calculated on the assumption that magnetic susceptibility of the solutions is the sum of the susceptibilities of the components.

$$\chi_{\text{sol}} = C_2 \chi_2 + \chi_w (1 - C_2).$$

C_s is the amount of CuCl_2 in 1 g. of the solution, χ_{sol} , χ_s and χ_w are the magnetic susceptibilities of the solutions, solute and the solvent respectively.

We find that values of the mass susceptibility of the solution actually obtained and those calculated from the above formulae do not agree indicating that some change has taken place in solution.

If we suppose that solvation takes place in solution, *i.e.* solute combines with the molecules of the solvent, the magnetic mass susceptibilities of CuCl_2 are not expected to change so much and moreover the deviations should have been regular.

FIG. 1.

It has been shown by previous workers that the magnetic moment of the same ion in solution varies slightly with concentrations and to somewhat greater extent with nature of the solvent. A further support is lent to the above results by the recent work of S. Dutta (*Phil. Mag.*, 1934, *iv*, 16, 585) on studies on paramagnetism. He has shown that in the case of Co and Ni^{2+} , the magnetic moments do not change very much when anhydrous salts pass from anhydrous state to the hydrated state. Ions and water dipoles surrounding the paramagnetic atom or ion are in the same relative position in two types of salts and give rise to the same field effect. In the case of coordination compounds, however, the crystalline field assumes an altogether different value due to interaction of new atomic grouping around the metallic ion.

FIG. 2.

Actually we get a marked change in the susceptibility of CuCl_2 in these solvents which goes against the hydration theory of Wiederman. This change, however, can be explained on the basis of complex ion theory. There is a sudden change in susceptibility where there is a change in colour. This is better explained from the accompanying graphs (Fig. 1) in which the results of magnetic susceptibility are plotted against the concentrations. There is a sharp break in the graph accompanying the change of colour; in other words a transition takes place.

From Tables V and VI we find that changes in magnetic susceptibility are regular and there is no change of colour in the solutions. The curves are straight lines as is shown by graphs IV and V (Fig. 2.).

Thus it is clear that the colour change is associated with a break in susceptibility-concentration curve and the colour change is due to the formation or dissociation of complex ions of the type $(\text{CuCl}_2)'$ and CuCl_4'' . These changes can be represented as

